

Long-term data for Europe

EURHISFIRM

M10.2 Final recommendations on business model
and governance

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BUSINESS MODEL

The proposed business model represents an approximation toward **sustainability** for EURHISFIRM in its transition from the implementation to the operation stage. The described scenarios will be continuously refined in light of the progress made with our user community. Therefore, this document should not be considered as a commitment to a final plan to be executed exactly as it is currently formulated, but rather as an essential guidance in the process of developing our final business plan.

The business model must ensure the sustainability of EURHISFIRM as a **Data-oriented International Distributed Research Infrastructure** specialized in the federation, management, storage and curation of large company-level historical datasets.

EURHISFIRM will operate on the base of a **central shared coordination model**, with distributed and operational nodes, and a coordinating mechanism based on a central node.

Key Partners

At the design stage of the Research Infrastructure, the members/partners of the EURHISFIRM consortium are 12 institutions from 8 countries. They include **universities, research centers and research infrastructures**. They participate in the research programme and are committed to provide the resources that will allow EURHISFIRM to move on to the implementation, and finally to the operation stage.

During this stage, we have identified **CESSDA (Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives)** as a key strategic partner, inviting them to join the project. CESSDA is now a full member of the EURHISFIRM consortium. The participation of GESIS-Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences (the largest German research infrastructure for social sciences) in EURHISFIRM has effectively ensured from the outset our co-ordination with CESSDA standards and practices and in-depth knowledge on RI design.

In the implementation stage, EURHIFIRM will deepen its coordination with CESSDA's standards and practices with the aim of integrating within its network of Service Providers in the operation stage.

EURHISFIRM also aims to integrate into the European open cloud ecosystem for social sciences and humanities promoted by the **SSHOC (Social Science and Humanities Open Cloud)** project, adopting the interoperability principles of FAIR data and developing cloud-ready tools.

EURHISFIRM is also open to collaborative partnerships with other RIs, digital libraries, archives and repositories, such as DARIAH-EU, Europeana and Clarin.

Key Activities

EURHIFIRM will supply three types of services:

- 1) **Data services** based on a **Wide Access mode** to raw data to guarantee the broadest possible access;
- 2) **Support, community building and training services to expand its user community;**
- 3) **Infrastructure services** for the production, standardization and enrichment of data from digitized primary sources.

EURHISFIRM also contemplates the possibility to offer additional value-added services requested by specific users for academic or commercial purposes.

Key Resources

EURHISFIRM key resources include:

- 1) **Data Extraction** using an Artificial Intelligence-based platform;
- 2) **Data Merging** in order to connect existing historical and contemporary company-level data;
- 3) a **European Common Data Model** with interfaces to the process architecture;
- 4) a **Common Data Access Service** to ensure the interoperability of different datasets;
- 5) **Data Visualization** to give users maximum contextual information.

Benefits

EURHISFIRM will generate both economic and socio-economic benefits.

In terms of **economic benefits**, the availability of FAIR research data through EURHISFIRM will translate into a significant reduction in time costs, storage costs, license costs and research retraction.

Jointly, **time spent and storage costs** account for 95% of the total cost of not having FAIR data, according to the European Commission. Their estimated cost is **€4,476 per researcher/year**, equivalent to 8.2% of the average annual salary of an academic researcher. Their total estimated cost for the European research community in economic, financial and business history is estimated to **€2,238,000 per year**. This is a lower bound, as the community of EURHISFIRM users will include a large number of researchers who only occasionally use historical data, both in the academic sector and in research centers of public and private institutions, such as regulators or central and commercial banks.

EURHISFIRM's **socio-economic benefits** include:

- 1) **research-enhancing effects** (through publications, citations, research grants, scientific users, research collaborations);
- 2) **research training and other educational and outreach activities;**
- 3) the production of **expert advice and resources in support of public policies;**
- 4) the development of **collaborative projects with non-academic partners.**

Beneficiaries

The main beneficiaries of EURHISFIRM will be researchers, universities, libraries, archives, research funding organization, other Research Infrastructures and e-infrastructures (digital libraries, archives and repositories). However, also non-academic research institutions, both public and private, will benefit from the existence of EURHISFIRM. The channels through which all stakeholders can benefit from EURHISFIRM range from the use of its services to the establishment of long-term partnerships, up to full membership.

Cost structure

We provide a first approximation to the human capital requirements of the coordinating central node and to its cost structure at the **start of the operation stage**, including personnel costs and costs related to the use of infrastructures and licenses. These are estimated to **€394,000 per year** approximately.

Funding Streams

As to funding, the costs of EURHISFIRM, including both the central node and the distributed nodes, will have to be covered by a core stream of long-term structural funding from public agencies. This is justified by the fact that EURHISFIRM's main beneficiaries are the international research community and the general public. Structural funding will cover EURHISFIRM's basic functionality, usability and support services. The funding of the central node will be shared by the consortium members, with contributions based on country GDP and the possibility to contribute in-kind. Individual members will be responsible for funding the operation of distributed nodes. As a complementary revenue stream, EURHISFIRM will pursue project funding as well as contracts or fees for additional value-added services requested by specific users for academic or commercial purposes.

GOVERNANCE

Legal Structure

During the stage of implementation of the research infrastructure, the EURHISFIRM consortium will operate on the base of a Memorandum of Cooperation Agreement signed by the participating institutions. As it enters the operation stage, EURHISFIRM will become a separate and independent legal entity with the ability to hire employees and carry out commercial activities.

The precise legal form of this independent entity will be decided at the end of the implementation stage.

Organization

At the operation stage, the governance model of this legal entity will be aligned to that of other RIs in the social sciences. It will be based on three main bodies:

- 1) a **General Assembly**;
- 2) an **Executive Committee**;
- 3) a **Scientific Advisory Board/Steering Committee**.

The General Assembly is the highest authority, composed by representatives of EURHISFIRM members and responsible for decisions about budget and long-term strategies. The Executive Committee reports to the Assembly and is composed of the Director of the central node, the Head of the Scientific Advisory Board/Steering Committee, and a Board of Directors (one for each participating country). The Steering Committee will be composed of experts from the EURHISFIRM network and from international independent experts.

In addition, we contemplate the possibility of a permanent **Stakeholder Forum** as an interface with stakeholders who are not members (hence, are not represented in the General Assembly).

Since EURHISFIRM will be a distributed RI, we are also considering the creation of a **Committee of National Coordinators**, to integrate and coordinate national activities at consortium level. Finally, for day-to-day management the Director will be supported by a Head Office located at the central node.

